

YAG OF THE STRUCTURE ACQUISITION , STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES

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Anatasia

The results of X-ray studies showed that since YAG and Nd: YAG single crystals have a body-centered cubic lattice with space group Ia3d, the lattice parameter for YAG $a = 1.1949$ nm and for Nd: YAG $a = 1.1961$ nm. The difference between the radii of Nd³⁺ ions (0.1247nm) and Y³⁺ (0.1158nm) is 8%, which leads to an increase in the unit cell parameter of Nd:YAG single crystals. After annealing YAG crystals in a reducing atmosphere, the formation of color centers was determined by charge coverage leading to a reduction in the number of growth defects acting as recipients .

Many oxides are used in laser materials, nonlinear optics, acousto-optics, optical data and magnetic memories, waves, etc. Yttrium-aluminum garnet (YAG, $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$) and yttrium-aluminum garnet coated with neodymium (Nd:YAG) are the most common types of oxide crystals widely used as active media in solid state lasers. Alloyed mixture - triply ionized neodymium Nd (III), usually replaces a small part of yttrium ions in the crystal structure of aluminum-yttrium pomegranate and provides lysing activity in the crystal.

The physical properties of the Nd:YAG crystal and the properties of laser devices based on them depend mainly on internal microstrains and defects. Thus, it is important from a physical and technological point of view to determine the

optimal technological conditions, structural values and physical properties of Yeg single crystals without Nd³⁺ impurities. In this regard, this work presents the results of studying the structural properties of YAG and Nd:YAG single crystals in recent years.

The research target is single crystal YAG and Nd:YAG grown by the generally accepted Chochral method [1,2]. The Chokhralsky method is used as a laser with medium and high power efficiency, which has great advantages for growing high-quality and large YAG and Nd:YAG single crystals. Using the Chokhralsky technique, the stable and equilibrating process of crystals is controlled by different values of the process. Small changes in growth values

Condition monitoring was performed on a third-generation Empryan Malvern PANalytical Ltd type X-ray diffractometer [2,3]. X-ray diffraction measurements were performed continuously in the Bragg-Brentano beam geometry from $2\theta = 10^\circ$ to 90° with a scanning speed of 0.33 grad/min and angular steps of 0.0200 (degree). X-ray diffraction for YAG and Nd:YAG single crystals experimental data obtained using the method:

YAG grown by Chochral method is given in Fig. 1. Analysis of monocrystalline YAG radiography shows that there are several systematic reflexes in the diffraction image (Fig. 1- a) of selective nature with different densities. Diffraction reflectance observed from YAG samples with YAG (2,420) at $2\theta = 33.6^\circ$ and its next order (840) at $2\theta = 69.9^\circ$, their full width values up to half of the reflection (FWHM (420) $\approx 3.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$ rad and FWHM (840) $4.473 \cdot 10^{-3}$ rad) cryst yttrium-aluminum of garnet perfection $a = 1.1949$ nm lattice of values value with shows . Experimental the results analysis YAG crystals Brave phase to the group incoming

group Ia3d - to has been volume centralized cube to the fence have that shows .

Figure 1. YAG (a) and of Nd:YAG (b) single crystals x-ray

can destabilize the system and directly affect the quality of the crystal. Structural and changes of samples studied by us

From this except , various different intensities with new systematic reflexes appear it has been ; (220)_{YAG} with $d/n = 4.2880 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 20.7^\circ$), (321)_{YAG} with $d/n = 3.241 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 27.5^\circ$), (400)_{YAG} with $d/n = 3.032 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 29.6^\circ$), (422)_{YAG} with $d/n = 2.476 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 36.3^\circ$), (222)_{YAG} with $d/n = 2.379 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 37.8^\circ$), (611)_{YAG} with $d/n = 1.967 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 46.1^\circ$), (640)_{YAG} with $d/n = 1.682 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 54.6^\circ$), d/n with (800)_{YAG} = $1.516 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 61.1^\circ$), (842)_{YAG} with $d/n = 1.323 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 71.3^\circ$) and d/n with (921)_{YAG} = $1.308 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 72.2^\circ$) your possession confirm addition opportunities Go to : on the site move , search ($2\theta = 54.6^\circ$), (800)_{YAG} $d/n = 1.516 \text{ \AA}$ with YAG ($2\theta = 61.1^\circ$), (842) you own confirm addition

opportunities for (921) YAG with $D/N = 1.308 \text{ \AA}$ ($2\theta = 72.2\theta$). Fig according to 1- p Nd: YAG of single crystals x-ray present is enough of YAG single crystals from radiography significant level difference does and by 42% main the intensity of the reflex (15). reduces ; of reflexes intensity

(840) turn with 2 times decreases and of reflexes intensity (220), (321), (400), (422), (222), (611), (640), (800), (842) and (921) one how many percent increased and they are Nd: YAG in the spectra smaller to the corners diffraction to change provides . With that together , s $d/n = 0.4951 \text{ nm}$ ($2\theta = 17.9^\circ$), li $d/n = 0.2144 \text{ nm}$ ($2\theta = 42.1^\circ$), li $d/n = 0.1751 \text{ nm}$ ($2\theta = 52.3^\circ$) and li $d/n = 0.1293 \text{ nm}$ ($2\theta = 73.2^\circ$) medium scattered in the corners uncomfortable background level uncomfortable nature _ Relatively net width ($\text{FWHM} = 4.36 * 10^{-3} \text{ rad}$) and big density (105 imp sec^{-1}) is the main reflex (420), as well as another even reflection carry on of procedures in radiography availability , Nd:YAG crystalline of the fence high level perfection shows and Nd: YAG spatial group with volumetric centered cube to the fence have Ia3d and with orientation (420). one crystalline . Nd for fence value : YAG $\alpha = 1.1961 \text{ nm}$, which is very less publication done data [3,4] ($12.011 \text{ \AA}$). Nd of the crystal cell value : 0.12% more than oil YAG crystal . Nd $^{3+}$ of ion radius (0.1247 nm) Y $^{3+}$ of ion larger than the radius (0.1158 nm). and difference by about 8% equal to is Nd $^{3+}$ of Y $^{3+}$ crystalline fence to the field input difficult not but _ cell of value to increase take will come . This is Nd:YAG in the diffractogram small spread to the corners looking systematic reflection to continue to change take will come .

Summary

So so , YAG and Nd single crystals derived : YAG ia3d spatial group with three measured cube has a grid.for AG fence value $\alpha = 1.1949 \text{ nm}$ and Nd for:YAG $\alpha = 1.1961 \text{ nm}$. Nd of the crystal cell value : 0.12% more than oil YAG crystal . Nd $^{3+}$ of ion radius (0.1247 nm) Y $^{3+}$ of ion larger than the radius (0.1158 nm). and difference by about 8% equal to is Nd $^{3+}$ of Y $^{3+}$ crystalline fence to the

field input difficult not but _ cell of value to increase take will come . of YAG crystals in the decrease evasive then of the color centers appear be divided was determined atmosphere charge cover receiver task which performs growth defects count to decrease take will come .

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